

VERSION 1

CMIP Data Disclaimer

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CMIP-IPO@esa.int

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CMIP International Project Office
ESA ECSAT
Fermi Avenue
Harwell Campus
Didcot, Oxfordshire
OX11 0FD, United Kingdom

Acknowledgements

This data disclaimer was prepared by the CMIP Panel and WIP co-chairs in consultation with WMO:

Helene Hewitt and John Dunne, CMIP Panel co-chairs

Matthew Mizielinski and James Anstey, WCRP ESMO Infrastructure Panel co-chairs

Daniel Trup, Legal Counsel, Office of Legal Counsel, World Meteorological Organization

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VERSION RECORD

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